

DEVELOPMENT OF DISCURSIVE COMPETENCE AMONG PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS.

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The development of discursive competence is included in a wide range of issues in the problem field of teaching foreign languages to students non-linguistic faculties. In the context of teaching a foreign language for general purposes, the problem of developing discursive competence of students of non-linguistic faculties receives particular importance and specificity.

The purpose of this work is to emphasize the importance of the formation of discursive competence as an integral part of the foreign language communicative competence of students of non-linguistic faculties, to focus on the complex essence of the concept of “discursive competence”, to show the usefulness of using in this regard an integrative differentiated approach to the development of discursive competence of students of non-linguistic faculties in the process of studying a foreign language block language for general purposes.

The key concepts for us are “foreign language communicative competence”, “discursive competence”, “discourse”, “integrative-differentiated approach”. Let us first consider the issue of the relationship and role of development of discursive competence and foreign language communicative competence of students of non-linguistic faculties. The development of communicative competence is noted among the priority goals identified by work programs for non-linguistic universities and faculties in the discipline “Foreign Language” and an exemplary program “Foreign Language” for non-linguistic universities and faculties, edited by S.G. Ter-Minasova. These programs emphasize that the developed foreign language communicative competence largely determines the effectiveness of communication between future graduates of non-linguistic faculties and foreign partners in various areas of cultural, every day, professional and scientific activity; opens up opportunities for the development of information culture and human self-improvement.

The concept of “foreign language communicative competence” is noted different approaches to its formulation and structural content. We will proceed from the definition proposed by E.V. Krasilnikova, in which foreign language communicative competence is “the ability of a future specialist to act in the mode of a secondary linguistic personality in a variety of socially determined

situations, readiness to carry out intercultural interaction” [10]. Emphasizing the multicomponent essence of foreign language communicative competence, a number of domestic and foreign researchers highlight discursive competence in its composition (I.A. Zimnyaya, V.V. Safonova, E.N. Solovova, D. Himes, E.A. Shaturnaya, A.N. . Shchukin and others).

According to S.K. Gural and E.A. Shaturna, discursive competence is “an integral substance of communicative competence and represents knowledge of various types of discourses and the rules of their construction, as well as the ability to create and understand them taking into account the communication situation” [6].

Most researchers point to the complex essence of discursive competence (S.K. Gural, I.A. Evstigneeva, E.A. Shaturnaya, etc.). As noted by I.A. Evstigneev, the development of discursive competence is determined by a number of developed discursive skills, including: the ability to understand, highlight, structure and apply lexical and grammatical resources of a foreign language; determine genres of texts; predict, evaluate and manage the direction of communication; build one’s own behavior in accordance with sociocultural and historical-cultural contexts, etc. [8]

Modern researchers consider discourse as a complex multicomponent self-organizing integral system (S.K. Gural, A.A. Kibrik, E.A. Shaturnaya, etc.). The system-forming characteristics of discourse, as indicated by A.A. Kibrik, they speak: types (modes), genres, functional styles, formality. A.A. Kibrik emphasizes that modern science has not developed a single comprehensive classification of types of discourse, and depending on the mode, genre, degree of formality and other indicators and “the multiplication of all these variables,” many different types of discourse can be identified [9].

Consequently, considering discourse as a basic component of discursive competence, the practical task arises of determining criteria for selecting types of discourse that contribute to the development of discursive competence. The solution to this problem I.V. Aleshchanova and N.A. Frolova see it in the analysis of the most frequently used types of discourses characteristic of typical communication situations of future specialists, and in the subsequent correlation and selection of discourses in accordance with the learning objectives. In the block of the training program for students of non-linguistic faculties in a foreign language for general purposes, a list of topics has been specified, the purpose of studying which is the development of functional communicative skills within the framework of educational, cognitive, every day

and socio-cultural spheres of communication. An important applied task in this regard is not only the selection of types of discourses that correspond to the learning objectives (according to I.V. Aleshchanova and N.A. Frolova [1]), but also, in our opinion, fitting them into the context of the communicative situation in accordance with the current level of discursive competence, previous experience of teaching a foreign language, individual characteristics of students. In other words, the use of an integrative-differentiated approach to learning.

Conclusion:

Based on the experiment, it was found that the intensification of foreign language discursive competence of applicants contributes to the study and better learning of foreign languages, the activation of speech activity, and text-making skills of different levels. It also contributes to a more active implementation of knowledge of a foreign language in its practical application of various types of discursive practices. The educational aspect of the training was important because the introduced course became useful for all participants, regardless of their social, age, communication abilities and profession.

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